

How much platinum is enough? Stability of Pt-coated titanium films for porous transport layers (PTLs) in acidic and fluoride-containing electrolyte

Gabriel C. da Silva^{a,b,*}, Xianxian Xie^c, Michael Vorochta^c, Ivan Khalakhan^c, Serhiy Cherevko^{a,*}

^a Helmholtz Institute Erlangen-Nürnberg for Renewable Energy (IET-2), Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH, Cauerstraße 1, 91058 Erlangen, Germany

^b Chemistry Department, Federal University of Viçosa, Av. Peter Henry Rolfs, 36570-900 Viçosa Brazil

^c Department of Surface and Plasma Science, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Charles University, 18000 Prague 8, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

Platinum-coated titanium porous transport layers (PTLs) are commonly used in proton exchange membrane water electrolyzers (PEMWE) to ensure electrical contact and corrosion resistance on the anode side. While the impact of platinum on interfacial performance has been extensively studied, the effect of Pt coating thickness on dissolution stability is still not well understood. In this study, model Pt/Ti thin films with tuned Pt thicknesses ranging from 1 to 100 nm are fabricated using magnetron sputtering. The films are examined using operando scanning flow cell inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (SFC-ICP-MS). Our findings reveal that thin Pt coatings do not block Ti dissolution under the tested conditions, while coatings of 20 nm or thicker substantially suppress Ti dissolution under specific dynamic operating protocols. In fluoride-containing electrolytes, the most robust and consistent suppression of Ti dissolution across all investigated conditions is achieved with 100 nm Pt coating. These results highlight critical Pt thickness thresholds necessary to suppress Ti corrosion under the operating conditions investigated here and provide a mechanistic foundation for the rational design of PTL coatings prior to validation at the device level.

1. Introduction

The production of green hydrogen through proton exchange membrane water electrolysis is expected to play a crucial role in decarbonizing the global energy system. It facilitates the energy storage and integration of intermittent renewable energy sources. However, proton exchange membrane water electrolyzers (PEMWE) face significant challenges, primarily due to high hydrogen production costs. To address these issues, it is essential to optimize not only the performance but also the operational lifespan of the entire system [1,2].

While significant efforts have been devoted to improving electrocatalysts for the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) and the oxygen evolution reaction (OER), the overall efficiency and durability of PEMWE also rely on advancements in other cell components, particularly the porous transport layer (PTL). This layer plays a crucial role in the electrolyzer architecture, facilitating the transport of water and gas while ensuring electronic conductivity and providing mechanical support [3,4]. Titanium-based PTLs are commonly used on the anode side due to their high corrosion resistance. Previous studies have demonstrated that various parameters, including the fabrication process,

thickness, porosity, and pore structure, influence the balance between fluid transport, electron conductivity, and mechanical stability, ultimately affecting the performance of the electrolyzer [5]. Nevertheless, titanium PTLs are not entirely immune to degradation under PEMWE conditions [6,7].

Importantly, titanium, whether used in PTLs, bipolar plates, or as catalyst supports, is susceptible to degradation in PEMWE environments. One primary degradation mechanism is surface passivation, which leads to the formation of a dense, insulating titanium dioxide (TiO₂) layer. This layer impairs electronic conductivity and degrades overall cell performance [8,9]. Furthermore, titanium can undergo electrochemical dissolution, releasing titanium species into the electrolyte [10–12]. These dissolved species may act as contaminants, hindering anode performance and potentially migrating through the membrane, where they can accumulate on the cathode side, compromising cell integrity [13,14].

Additionally, the degradation of other cell components, such as the release of fluorine-containing species from the membrane or ionomer, can lead to chemical reactions with titanium oxide, further compromising its stability [15,16]. Similar degrading effects have been reported

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: gabriel.christiano@ufv.br (G.C. da Silva), s.cherevko@fz-juelich.de (S. Cherevko).

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for other chemical contaminants, including chloride ions and hydrogen peroxide [17]. To mitigate these issues, Ti-based PTLs are often coated with a thin layer of noble metal, typically platinum, gold, or iridium [9, 18]. Such coatings can significantly enhance the performance and durability of PEM electrolyzers by improving corrosion resistance, maintaining electrical conductivity, and reducing charge transfer resistance at the interface between the catalyst layer and the PTL [19–21].

Comparing different coatings, Liu et al. demonstrated that, despite showing similar initial performance, Au-coated titanium PTLs are less stable than their Ir- and Pt-coated counterparts. A 35 % decline in performance was observed after a 4,000-hour test, attributed to the delamination and dissolution of the gold [20]. In their subsequent work, the authors optimized the iridium loading in the PTL [22]. They found that increasing the iridium loadings from 0.025 to 0.05 mg/cm² did not result in any performance gains, indicating that the iridium loading could be reduced. On the other hand, the stability of these coatings has not been assessed. Other studies have also explored the use of iridium-coated PTLs [23–25]. However, platinum remains the most common choice for coating PTLs in commercial applications.

Like iridium, many studies have focused on the protective role and performance improvement of platinum coatings in titanium PTLs. Wang et al. investigated PTLs with Pt coating thicknesses ranging from 0.1 to 0.7 μm [26]. Their findings showed that excessively thick coatings increase mass transfer resistance at high current densities, which hinders gas-liquid transport within the PTL. By promoting water channels through laser ablation, the authors enhanced mass transfer efficiency, thereby improving the performance of the electrolyzer. Geuß et al. [21] contributed to optimizing platinum-coated PTLs by highlighting the critical role of the interface between the PTL and the iridium-based catalyst layer in determining overall OER performance. In particular, the incorporation of thin platinum interlayers onto titanium PTLs has significantly enhanced the activity of amorphous IrO_x catalysts by reducing interfacial charge transport barriers. Without platinum, the contact between amorphous IrO_x and the native TiO_x layer of the PTL often results in the formation of Schottky-type junctions [27], which increases the overpotential and limits catalyst utilization. The presence of a platinum interlayer mitigates these effects by creating a more ohmic contact, thereby enhancing electronic conductivity across the interface and facilitating more efficient utilization of the catalyst layer.

Other works have focused on reducing the Pt loading in PTLs by using transition metals as interlayers between Pt and Ti, such as Mo, W, Nb, and Ta [28–30]. Recently, Anurag et al. reported that a multilayer Nb/Pt coating (Nb = 350 nm and Pt = 50 nm) deposited on a Ti PTL exhibited superior corrosion resistance and longer simulated durability compared to a commercial Pt/Ti PTL with a 200 nm Pt layer [31]. The gains achieved through Pt coatings in PTLs may not be beneficial without sufficient stability. In this context, Jing et al. prepared sputtered Pt films with three different thicknesses (6, 11, and 17 nm) on Ti substrates by controlling the sputtering time and tested them for 48 h at 2.054 V vs. SHE in a three-electrode cell using 0.5 mol L⁻¹ electrolyte containing 2 ppm fluoride. The authors highlighted that Pt thickness is a crucial factor in determining durability and concluded that coating failure was primarily caused by delamination rather than by Pt dissolution. Nonetheless, Pt dissolution was not monitored *operando*, which may lead to artifacts during post-test sampling as a consequence of coating detachment. Moreover, the dissolution of the underlying Ti substrate was not assessed [32].

On the other hand, Cho et al. demonstrated that even commercial PTLs, covered by Pt or IrO₂, are susceptible to titanium dissolution [33]. This dissolution can lead to the detachment of the platinum coating, resulting in a significant decrease in electrical conductivity. Furthermore, the dissolved platinum can redeposit on the membrane [34], negatively impacting the lifespan of the PEMWE. To improve the stability and cost-effectiveness of PTL performance, it is essential to optimize the amount of platinum used in PTL coatings.

Despite recent advances, the effect of Pt layer thickness on both

platinum and titanium dissolution under conditions relevant to PEMWE is still not well defined. Specifically, it remains unclear how thin a Pt coating can be while still effectively preventing Ti corrosion and minimizing Pt loss. While studies involving gas diffusion electrodes or PEMWE assemblies are essential for evaluating performance at the device level, they do not readily allow for the direct, time-resolved quantification of dissolved species originating from the PTL. In this work, we utilize a scanning flow cell coupled with inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (SFC-ICP-MS). This technique enables sensitive monitoring of Pt and Ti dissolution from well-defined Pt/Ti model films with controlled thickness prepared by magnetron sputtering, facilitating a precise examination of how thickness affects dissolution behavior and the protective capabilities of the coatings. This approach offers practical insights into the relationship between Pt layer thickness and the dissolution of both Pt and Ti. It helps establish protection limits before transitioning to more complex and realistic electrolyzer environments.

2. Experimental section

To investigate the influence of platinum layer thickness on porous transport layers' stability, Pt/Ti films were used as a model and fabricated via magnetron sputtering. The depositions were carried out using a magnetron sputtering system with three circular TORUS DC magnetrons (Kurt J. Lesker). Initially, the chamber was evacuated to a base pressure of 10⁻⁴ Pa and filled with argon to a working pressure of 0.6 Pa. A 100 nm thick titanium adhesion layer was first deposited onto silicon wafers using a 2" Ti target (99.99 %, Kurt J. Lesker), followed by platinum layers of varying nominal thicknesses (1, 3, 5, 10, 20, 50, and 100 nm), deposited using a 2" Pt target (99.99 %, Safina). All depositions were performed without exposing the samples to air. The Pt layer thickness was controlled by adjusting the deposition time, as described in the Supporting Information. The deposition conditions were selected to produce compact Pt films rather than grainy, porous layers [35].

The morphology of the as-deposited layers was analyzed using a Mira 3 (Tescan) microscope operating at a primary electron energy set at 30 keV. Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) was performed with an XFlash 610 detector (Bruker) integrated into a Mira 3 (Tescan) scanning electron microscope (SEM) operating at the primary electron energy set at 20 keV. The XPS measurements were performed in a laboratory system provided by SPECS Surface Nano Analysis GmbH in an ultrahigh vacuum (10⁻⁹ mbar) analysis chamber equipped with a monochromated Al K_α X-ray source (hν = 1486.6 eV) and a multi-channel electron energy analyzer (SPECS Phoibos 150) with 1D-DLD detector.

The dissolution stability of Pt/Ti films was investigated using a polycarbonate scanning flow cell coupled with inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (SFC-ICP-MS, PerkinElmer NexION 350X) [36]. A graphite rod and an Ag/AgCl (3 mol L⁻¹) electrode were employed as the counter and reference electrodes, respectively. The cell aperture defined a geometric surface area of the Pt/Ti films of 0.00907 cm². The electrolyte flow rate in the SFC was approximately 3.2 μL s⁻¹, rapidly removing dissolved species from the electrode surface. Electrochemical measurements were performed in argon-purged 0.1 mol L⁻¹ HClO₄ (70 %, Merck) at 25 °C. All potentials were converted to the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) scale. ICP-MS calibration was carried out daily using standard solutions containing the analytes in concentrations ranging from 0 to 5 ppb. Platinum and titanium dissolution were monitored by tracking the ¹⁹⁵Pt and ⁴⁸Ti isotopes. Internal standard solutions containing 10 μg L⁻¹ of ¹⁸⁷Re and ⁴⁵Sc were used to ensure consistent performance.

Two electrochemical protocols were developed and used to assess the stability of the Pt/Ti films:

I) A cyclic voltammetry protocol composed of three stages was employed. First, the potential was held at 0.1 V for 300 s to stabilize the system, followed by two cyclic voltammograms (CVs) recorded between 0.1 and 1.5 V at a scan rate of 10 mV s⁻¹. After another 300-second hold

at 0.1 V, 40 CVs were recorded within the same potential range but at a scan rate of 200 mV s^{-1} . A final 300-second hold at 0.1 V was applied before recording the last two CVs at 10 mV s^{-1} . This protocol was designed to simulate alternating reductive and oxidative conditions relevant to PEMWE operation, namely reductive environments induced by hydrogen crossover and oxidative conditions associated with oxygen evolution at the anode. The dynamic potential cycling intentionally accelerates repeated oxide formation and reduction processes, allowing transient dissolution phenomena at the Pt/Ti interface to be probed within experimentally accessible time scales.

II) Five galvanostatic pulses between 0 and 1 mA cm^{-2} , each lasting 300 s. This galvanostatic protocol was selected to mimic start-stop events in PEMWE operation, during which the electrode experiences repeated transitions between open-circuit or low-current conditions and anodic polarization. While the applied current densities are lower than those encountered in technical devices, this approach provides a controlled framework to assess thickness-dependent dissolution behavior under repeated polarization transients.

Electrochemical measurements were also conducted in a mixed electrolyte containing $0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ HClO}_4$ and KF (99.99 %, Thermo Fisher) to evaluate the influence of fluoride ions on the dissolution behavior, with a final KF concentration of 0.1 mmol L^{-1} ($\sim 2 \text{ ppm}$), representing fluoride levels that may arise from the degradation of perfluorosulfonic acid (PFSA) membranes under PEMWE operation, as reported in the literature [37]. These experiments were conducted on Pt/Ti samples with platinum thicknesses of 0, 1, 20, and 100 nm.

3. Results

The model Pt/Ti films with varying Pt thicknesses were initially characterized by SEM-EDX and XPS, and the results are presented in Fig. 1. The EDX and XPS analyses confirm the successful preparation of Pt/Ti films with progressively increasing Pt coverage. SEM imaging

shows that magnetron sputtering does not yield ideally compact Pt layers, particularly for thicknesses up to 5 nm, where the growth proceeds via island formation and partial coalescence rather than the development of a continuous film. This discontinuous morphology implies that, at low thicknesses, significant regions of the Ti substrate remain exposed or are only weakly covered by Pt, which is expected to influence both the electrochemical behavior and the corrosion resistance of the system.

Interestingly, the XPS results shown in Fig. 1c reveal a clear thickness-dependent evolution of the electronic state of platinum. For the 1 and 3 nm films, the Pt^0 4f peak is shifted toward lower binding energies when compared to thicker coatings, indicating a modified electronic environment. This behavior is consistent with strong Pt–Ti interfacial interactions and possible electron transfer from the Ti (or TiO_x) substrate to the Pt overlayer, rendering the Pt more electron-rich [38,39]. As the Pt thickness increases, the Pt 4f signal gradually shifts toward the characteristic binding energy of bulk metallic Pt, reflecting the progressive dominance of Pt–Pt interactions and the reduced influence of the underlying titanium. This transition highlights the change from an interface-dominated regime in ultrathin films to a more bulk-like electronic structure in thicker coatings, which is directly relevant for understanding their protective efficiency and dissolution stability.

To investigate the effect of platinum layer thickness on the stability of PTLs, we initially employed CVs in a voltage range from 0.1 to 1.5 V. Fig. 2a shows the platinum dissolution profiles for films with platinum nominal thicknesses of 1, 20, and 100 nm. The characteristic transient dissolution of platinum is evident during the initial slow CV scans, displaying a minor dissolution peak during the positive scan and a more pronounced peak during the reverse scan [40,41].

In the subsequent 40 fast CV cycles, we observed an increase in platinum dissolution, culminating in more significant dissolution during the final two slow CV scans compared to the initial ones. This

Fig. 1. (a) SEM images of the uncoated Ti substrate and Pt/Ti films with different Pt thicknesses. (b) EDX spectra and (c) high-resolution Ti 2p and Pt 4f XPS spectra of the corresponding samples.

Fig. 2. (a) Platinum dissolution profiles for films with 1, 20, and 100 nm Pt coatings. The top panel shows the applied potential during the CV protocol (1.1–1.5 V). (b) CVs recorded for the Pt(20 nm)/Ti film at the beginning of the test (BOT) and the end of the test (EOT). Measurements were performed in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ HClO₄ electrolyte.

progressive increase in dissolution indicates the growth of the electrochemically active platinum surface area throughout the cycling protocol, as evidenced by the CV profiles recorded at the beginning and end of the test (see Figs. 2b and S1).

It is important to note that the PtO-reduction peak in Figs. 2b and S1 become more pronounced toward the end of the test, whereas changes in the Hupd region remain comparatively smaller. Since the PtO reduction feature is sensitive to the extent and kinetics of Pt oxidation [42], this evolution may indicate subtle modifications of the Pt surface during cycling. As supported by the XPS results discussed earlier, the thinnest Pt coatings exhibit an electronic environment influenced by the underlying Ti/TiO_x. Similar metal–support interactions have been reported for Pt/TiO₂ systems [43–45], and such effects may contribute to the observed changes in the PtO/Pt redox region after repeated cycling.

In addition, potential cycling may remove surface species originating from the sputtering process, presumably residual TiO_x present within discontinuous ultrathin films, which would progressively expose a larger fraction of metallic Pt sites. This electrochemical cleaning could also contribute to the increased definition of the PtO-reduction peak at later stages of the experiment.

Since platinum dissolution occurs, the thickness of the Pt layer may not be sufficient to entirely prevent the dissolution of the underlying titanium, particularly in the presence of coating inhomogeneities or structural defects such as pinholes, cracks, or local delamination that expose the Ti surface to the electrolyte. This limitation is further aggravated for thin Pt coatings (≤ 5 nm), which, as discussed above, tend to exhibit discontinuous growth and incomplete surface coverage, inherently increasing the vulnerability of the Ti substrate to exposure and corrosion [32].

The titanium dissolution profiles during cycling are shown in Fig. 3, which includes results obtained for the non-platinized sample. A

pronounced dissolution peak occurs during the first slow CV for the uncoated sample, with an onset potential around 0.77 V. In the second cycle, titanium dissolution markedly decreases, and even after 40 accelerated CV cycles, no significant titanium dissolution is observed. This behavior indicates the passivation of the titanium surface due to the formation of TiO_x under the applied conditions.

In the case of coated films, even a thin 1 nm coating of Pt significantly reduces Ti dissolution during the initial cycles. When the platinum layer is 5 nm or thicker, titanium dissolution becomes negligible during the first two cycles of the testing protocol (see Fig. S2). However, during the accelerated scans, an increase in Ti dissolution is observed in the platinum/titanium samples, a phenomenon not seen in the bare titanium electrode. This behavior is consistent for platinum coatings up to 50 nm (refer to Fig. S2). In contrast, titanium dissolution remains nearly undetectable with a 100 nm Pt layer throughout the entire electrochemical procedure.

To further probe dissolution under transient electrochemical conditions relevant to PEMWE operation, a sequence of current pulses between 0 and 1 mA cm⁻² was applied (protocol II). Although these currents are far below those in real devices, this protocol captures potential excursions and transient redox environments associated with start-up/shutdown and load fluctuations. The resulting Ti and Pt dissolution profiles for the uncoated Ti and Pt(20 nm)/Ti films are shown in Fig. 4a.

Under galvanostatic pulses, the bare Ti surface does not remain passivated; instead, measurable Ti dissolution is detected during the 1 mA cm⁻² holds. Because Ti is not catalytically active for the OER, the electrode potential increases above 3 V (Fig. 4b) to sustain the imposed current, leading to the breakdown of the passivated TiO₂ layer. This likely promotes the formation of soluble TiO₂⁺ and TiO₂²⁺ species [33]. Although such high potentials are not expected in functional PEMWE

Fig. 3. Titanium dissolution profiles for the studied uncoated (w/o Pt), 1, 20, and 100 nm Pt/Ti films during the CV protocol. Measurements were performed in $0.1 \text{ mol l}^{-1} \text{ HClO}_4$ electrolyte.

Fig. 4. (a) Dissolution profiles of titanium and platinum for the uncoated (w/o Pt) and 20 nm platinum-coated titanium films during current pulses ranging from 0 to 1 mA cm^{-2} (protocol II). The gray shaded areas indicate the periods during which the samples were polarized at 1 mA cm^{-2} . (b) Corresponding potential response during the galvanostatic pulses. (c) Magnified view of panel (b) highlighting the potential behavior of the Pt-coated films.

cells containing Ir-based OER catalysts, similar Ti dissolution has been reported under potentiostatic pulses between 1.0 and 2.0 V [46], conditions more representative of practical operation, indicating that titanium corrosion remains a concern unless an adequate noble-metal coating is present.

A Pt-thickness-dependent protection trend is evident in Fig. S3. Films with 1 and 3 nm Pt behave similarly to bare Ti, exhibiting persistent Ti dissolution, whereas 5 and 10 nm Pt coatings restrict it primarily to the first pulse. For Pt layers ≥ 20 nm, no detectable Ti dissolution occurs, indicating a threshold thickness required to fully protect the titanium substrate under transient loads.

Regarding platinum, comparison between protocols I (Fig. 2) and II (Fig. 4a) shows markedly lower Pt dissolution during the galvanostatic steps. Since the open-circuit potential (OCP) remains above 1.0 V during the resting periods (Fig. 4b and 4c), the Pt surface does not experience complete reduction, thereby suppressing the transient dissolution that typically accompanies re-oxidation [41]. Importantly, such transient Pt dissolution would ideally not occur during controlled PEMWE operation. Yet, these experiments demonstrate that potential excursions toward more reducing values, even if brief, may trigger measurable Pt loss and compromise the long-term integrity of Pt-coated PTLs.

The dissolved Ti and Pt amounts for each protocol can be determined by integrating the dissolution profiles. The integrated values are summarized in Fig. S4, while Fig. 5 presents the same data on a logarithmic scale to facilitate comparison across orders of magnitude. Figs. 5a and S4a show the dissolved amounts of each element during fast potential cycling (protocol I). A clear trade-off is observed between the thickness of the Pt coating and the protection provided to Ti; specifically, there is an exponential decrease in the amount of dissolved Ti as the Pt coverage increases from 1 nm (approximately 80 ng Ti cm^{-2}) to 100 nm (below the detection limit). In contrast, the dissolution of Pt increases for samples with thicker coatings.

Notably, the relatively high Ti dissolution observed in the Pt(1 nm)/Ti sample during fast cycling indicates that this ultrathin Pt layer does not provide stable protection under these dynamic conditions. Although Ti areas not covered by Pt are expected to oxidize and passivate during the initial slow scans, progressive Pt dissolution and morphological reorganization during the fast scans can expose a fresh Ti surface, thereby promoting additional Ti dissolution.

In the case of galvanostatic pulses (Figs. 5b and S4b), platinum

dissolved during the protocol remains relatively constant across the studied films, at about 10 ng cm^{-2} . The uncoated sample has a titanium dissolution rate of approximately 160 ng cm^{-2} . However, the sample with a 5 nm Pt coating over Ti shows a dissolved amount of around 25 ng cm^{-2} , representing an 85 % reduction. For samples with Pt coatings of 20, 50, and 100 nm, the dissolution of Ti becomes negligible, as discussed in Fig. 3.

The degradation of the PEMWE membrane can result in the presence of fluorinated species, which can also be detrimental to the PTL. Therefore, the protective effect of Pt coatings on PTLs was evaluated in the presence of fluoride ions. Fig. 6 displays the dissolution of the uncoated Ti and Pt(20 nm) and Pt(100 nm)/Ti films during CVs.

The presence of fluoride ions leads to an increased dissolution rate of Pt compared to that observed in HClO_4 (Fig. 6a). This effect is expected to destabilize the PTL by exposing more titanium. The Ti dissolution profiles for Pt/Ti films measuring 20 nm and 100 nm, as well as uncoated Ti films, are shown in Fig. 6b. Notably, the uncoated samples demonstrate higher dissolution rates for Ti than those presented in Fig. 3. Furthermore, there is no indication of passivation in the film, as dissolution peaks are also observed in the final two CV scans and a clear anodic signal at the end of the test, distinct from the behavior in fluoride-free electrolyte (Fig. S5). The Pt(20 nm) coating effectively protected the Ti layer during the initial slow scans. However, some Ti dissolution was observed during 40 fast scans (magnified view provided in Fig. S6). In contrast, the Pt(100 nm) coating maintained Ti dissolution levels below the detection limit throughout the experiment.

The protective role of the Pt coating in the presence of fluoride was also evaluated under current pulses (Fig. 7). The drastic increase in Ti dissolution for the uncoated sample is even more evident in protocol (II), where, starting from the third pulse, the Ti dissolution rate decreases as the film becomes almost completely removed. In contrast, the 20 nm Pt layer effectively suppressed Ti loss, thereby extending, to some extent, the overall stability of the film.

4. Discussion

The influence of Pt coating thickness on the electrochemical stability of Ti substrates was investigated under acidic conditions relevant to PEM water electrolysis. Although much of the current development of PTLs has focused on improving interfacial conductivity and catalytic

Fig. 5. Titanium and platinum dissolution amounts during (a) protocol I and (b) protocol II. Missing data points arise from the use of the logarithmic scale, since the amount of Ti dissolved is below the limit of detection of the ICP-MS. Data obtained in $0.1 \text{ mol l}^{-1} \text{ HClO}_4$ are shown as filled symbols, whereas open symbols correspond to measurements in fluoride-containing electrolyte.

Fig. 6. (a) Platinum dissolution profiles for Pt/Ti films with Pt thicknesses of 20 and 100 nm, and (b) titanium dissolution profiles for the uncoated Ti film and Pt/Ti films with Pt thicknesses of 20 and 100 nm, measured in $0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ HClO}_4 + 0.1 \text{ mmol L}^{-1} \text{ KF}$. For comparison, dissolution data obtained in fluoride-free HClO_4 are also included.

Fig. 7. Dissolution profiles of titanium and platinum for the uncoated (w/o Pt) and 20 nm platinum-coated titanium films during current pulses ranging from 0 to 1 mA cm^{-2} in $0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ HClO}_4 + 0.1 \text{ mmol L}^{-1} \text{ KF}$. The gray shaded areas indicate the periods during which the samples were polarized at 1 mA cm^{-2} .

utilization, considerably less attention has been devoted to understanding how ultrathin Pt layers perform in terms of dissolution stability. By employing Pt/Ti films with controlled Pt thickness, this study isolates other effects that may arise from the complex morphology of real PTLs.

4.1. Dissolution stability

Under cyclic voltammetry in fluoride-free electrolyte, the uncoated Ti film displays a pronounced dissolution peak during the first cycle, consistent with the formation of a protective TiO_2 layer. After this initial passivation, the dissolution of Ti becomes negligible. For Pt-coated

samples, the expected transient Pt dissolution behavior associated with oxide formation and reduction is observed [41]. Even relatively thin Pt layers (5 nm) suppress Ti dissolution during initial scans. However, SEM analysis indicates that ultrathin Pt coatings do not form fully compact films but rather exhibit discontinuous or partially coalesced morphologies, suggesting that portions of the Ti substrate may remain exposed from the outset. Therefore, Ti dissolution in these samples is likely influenced not only by progressive Pt loss during cycling, but also by the intrinsic morphology and incomplete surface coverage of the thinner Pt layers. In contrast, a 100 nm Pt layer fully protects the Ti throughout the experiment.

To contextualize the magnitude of Pt loss, assuming an approximate mass of 400 ng cm⁻² per monolayer (ML) of platinum and a density of 21.45 g cm⁻³, the integrated dissolution corresponds to roughly 0.14–0.30 ML, or ~0.03–0.06 nm of Pt. While these values appear small, they account for ~3 % of a 1 nm Pt film, illustrating how ultrathin coatings may rapidly approach the limit where isolated defects or Pt restructuring expose the underlying titanium. In addition to dissolution, repeated cycling to high potentials can induce morphological changes in the Pt layer, such as redistribution, agglomeration, or partial coalescence, which may lead to loss of film continuity and the formation of preferential pathways for electrolyte access to the Ti substrate. These effects are expected to be more pronounced for ultrathin films and may further facilitate Ti exposure over time [47].

To complement cyclic conditions, galvanostatic pulses were applied to emulate transient operational events. Under these pulses, the bare Ti film fails to remain stable: lacking OER activity, the potential exceeds 3 V, driving Ti oxidation and dissolution through the formation of soluble titanium species. Increasing Pt thickness progressively suppresses Ti dissolution, and coatings ≥20 nm provide adequate protection under this protocol. Platinum dissolution is markedly lower than during cycling because the open-circuit potential remains above ~1.0 V, avoiding complete reduction of Pt oxides and the associated transient dissolution. Nevertheless, potential excursions toward more reducing values — such as those arising from hydrogen crossover — could trigger renewed Pt loss and compromise coating integrity over time.

4.2. Fluoride-containing electrolyte

Fluoride ions introduce a more aggressive degradation environment. In the presence of 0.1 mmol L⁻¹ (~2 ppm) F⁻, the uncoated Ti film experiences sustained dissolution with no evidence of stable passivation, consistent with the known instability of TiO₂ in acidic fluoride media and formation of [TiF₆]²⁻ complexes [48]. Pt coatings improve stability, yet dissolution increases relative to fluoride-free electrolyte. Thin Pt layers offer only partial protection, while the 20 nm coating delays Ti dissolution but cannot entirely prevent it during accelerated potential cycling. The 100 nm film remains stable throughout its lifetime.

Fluoride also accelerates Pt loss. For the Pt (20 nm) film, the integrated Pt dissolution during CVs reaches approximately 340 ng cm⁻² (~0.90 monolayers, ~0.17 nm), substantially higher than in the fluoride-free electrolyte. During galvanostatic pulses, this effect is less pronounced, reinforcing the role of Pt-oxide reduction cycles in driving dissolution. These results contrast with earlier reports suggesting negligible Pt dissolution in the presence of fluoride [49].

4.3. Implications - from model to real PTLs

Although sputtered thin films do not reproduce the full morphology of commercial PTLs, they provide a controlled platform for isolating how Pt-layer thickness affects stability. The results suggest that even relatively small Pt losses can become relevant for ultrathin coatings, as localized thinning or restructuring may expose Ti and initiate corrosion processes. In addition, dissolution is unlikely to remain confined to the interface: dissolved Pt may re-deposit within the membrane or ionomer phase. At the same time, Ti species can migrate toward the membrane or

catalyst layer, potentially contributing to the growth of interfacial resistance or catalyst poisoning over extended operation [34,50].

In this context, although thicker Pt coatings dissolve more Pt in absolute terms, they are more effective in preventing Ti exposure, with coatings ≥20 nm already reducing dissolution during transient operation, and 100 nm required to suppress Ti dissolution even in the presence of fluoride. These observations offer a useful reference for defining practical lower limits for protective Pt layers and may help guide the design of durable PTLs before transitioning to more complex GDE or MEA-based validation.

5. Conclusion

In this work, we investigated how platinum-layer thickness influences the dissolution stability of Ti-based model PTLs under PEMWE-relevant conditions using operando SFC-ICP-MS. Beyond its established role in improving interfacial performance, Pt coating thickness was found to be a key factor controlling resistance to dissolution-induced degradation. Thin Pt layers can expose Ti, enabling corrosion. In contrast, coatings around ~20 nm already delay Ti exposure under specific transient operating conditions, while thicker layers (100 nm) provide the most robust protection and suppress Ti dissolution across all investigated conditions, even in the presence of fluoride. Although thicker Pt films dissolve more Pt in absolute terms, they maintain a continuous barrier and therefore offer superior protection over time. Overall, these results demonstrate that Pt thickness must be optimized not only with respect to catalytic and interfacial performance but also for long-term stability. The thickness thresholds identified here provide practical guidance for the rational design of durable PTLs within the investigated parameter space, and the mechanistic insight gained from this thin-film model system offers a foundation for translation to real porous structures and device-level operation.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT (OpenAI) in order to perform language proofreading and improve the clarity and readability of the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Gabriel C. da Silva reports financial support was provided by National Council for Scientific and Technological Development. Gabriel C. da Silva reports financial support was provided by Minas Gerais State Foundation of Support to the Research. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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